

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 7 / 4 / 194 TAKE OFF 0936Z H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A 320
LANDING 1649

PROJECT OFFICER :
AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A. KAYE
FLIGHT LEADER: M. SMITH
OBSERVER: VACC C. O'DOWD
OTHERS: CLOUD P. H. GREENSMITH
OZONE J. KENT
(A22) G. JENKINS

CAPTAIN: H. BURGOYNE
CO-PILOT: BILL
NAVIGATOR: E. HEATEN
ENGINEER: R. PRICE
LOADMASTER: J. CANNING.

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):
OPERATING AREA:

S.W. OF IRELAND

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME: 06Z

SORTIE BRIEF: 07 APRIL 1994

Variation of Aerosol Composition and Concentration and Concentration VACC

- 1) SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To determine the vertical structure of sea-salt and non-sea-salt sulphate aerosol in a clean marine boundary layer.
- 2) LOCATION:** West/SouthWest of Ireland [50-52 N, 8-15 W]
- 3) WEATHER:** Non-precipitating conditions with as little vertical mixing as possible. Air mass must be clean maritime
- 4) FLIGHT PATTERN:**
- a1) Profile out of Chivenor from 50ft to 20K at 1000 ft/min
 - a2) Transit to experimental location at transit speed
 - b) Execute a profile to 50 ft in cloud free air if possible. 1,000ft/min until in the marine boundary layer then 500ft/min (30 min).
 - c) Conduct a K-GAMMA wind field calibration (5min).
 - d) VACC horizontal runs will be conducted at (1) 100ft above sea-level, 1,000ft and two other levels yet to be determined (25 min each). Each VACC run will comprise two figure of eight race tracks across wind (total of four 5-minute legs, one for each heater tube and a one minute turn). A fifth run may be required depending on conditions. In between VACC runs profile at 500ft/min.
 - e) On completion of stack, terminate the scientific part of the flight with a profile down to 50ft @ 500ft/min. followed immediately by profile to 27K at 500 ft/min to cloud top then 1000 ft/min.
- Total Duration** Transit 3-4 hours
VACC 3-3.5 hours

Diplomatic clearance over Ireland not needed

Met Synops: The weather was dominated in the Atlantic and the forecast for the task area was for showers & hail, very convective cloud tops at about 11Kft.

In actual fact the conditions were quite different when we got to the task area. It was broken stratocumulus with a base of 3 1/2 Kft and cloud tops at 5 1/2 Kft.

Summary.

Initially we transited to Chivener ~~to~~ and descended to 50ft to profile up to 20Kft. This profile ~~for~~ was primarily for the ozone. We then transited to the task area and identified a suitable area of broken SC to work with, and commenced a profile descent to 50ft. We then ~~performed~~ executed a K-8 run at 100 ft and loitered for a short while ~~while~~ while the VACC operator re-calibrated the ~~VACC~~ ASASP-X laser. We operated depressurized from this point until PS. out of the task area.

Once the laser was operational we descended to 100ft. and started the 4 legs of the VACC runs. These were performed at 100, 1000, and 2000 ft. Between the 1000 and 2000 ft runs we profiled to 7Kft to determine cloud base and cloud tops. We did one 10 minute run at ~~the~~ 4000 in cloud and then a reciprocal perpendicular run through the entire cloud depth. ~~After~~ the final VACC run was ~~performed~~ performed at 7000 ft, 500ft above cloud tops.

We then climbed to 15Kft and profiled to 50ft through the task area and then out of the area with ~~and~~ a profile out of the area to a height ~~of~~ of 27Kft. and

A320 07-APR-94 Height time series

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

1 second averages

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms:	Form Title
$\frac{1}{7}$ 1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements Interactive log
1 2 4 2	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
2	MCR log CCN log MARSS log Chemistry log (OZONE)
6 - 2	Particulate/Filter boom Operator's log 2DK/FSSP/Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
1 ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Signal register Weather charts Satellite pictures Omega track Electronics pre-flight Mechanical fit

A320 7th April, 1994

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
093643		Take off from BOSCOMBE		
100646(1)-102626(2)		Profile P1	50ft->FL200	280 deg
113442(3)-115002(4)		Profile P2	FL200->50ft	310/110deg
120402(8)-120603(9)		K-GAMMA Run 1.1	100ft	140 deg
120836(10)-121127(11)		K-GAMMA Run 1.2	100ft	320 deg
VACC Runs				
123803(12)-124304(13)		Run 2.1	100ft	210 deg
124516(14)-125016(15)		Run 2.2	100ft	060 deg
125242(16)-125742(17)		Run 2.3	100ft	210 deg
125954(18)-130454(19)		Run 2.4	100ft	060 deg
130822(20)-131322(21)		Run 3.1	1000ft	220 deg
131541(22)-132045(23)		Run 3.2	1000ft	030 deg
132227(24)-132735()		Run 3.3	1000ft	220 deg
132851(25)-133351(26)		Run 2.4	1000ft	050 deg
133419(27)-133847(28)		Profile P3.1	1000ft->5800ft	240 deg
133847(28)-134236(29)		Profile P3.2	5800ft->2000ft	
134435(30)-134954(31)		Run 4.1	2000ft	040 deg
135149(32)-135649(33)		Run 4.2	2000ft	220 deg
135825(34)-140325(35)		Run 4.3	2000ft	040 deg
140532(36)-141032(37)		Run 4.4	2000ft	210 deg
141214(38)-142237(39)		Run 5.1	4000ft	040 deg
142523(40)-143011(41)		Profile P4.1	7500ft->2800ft	240 deg
143011(41)-143524(42)		Profile P4.2	2800ft->7000ft	220 deg

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
143733 (44)	-144236 (45)	Run 6.1	7000ft	050 deg
144408 (46)	-144909 (47)	Run 6.2	7000ft	210 deg
145035 (48)	-145536 (49)	Run 6.3	7000ft	030 deg
145649 (50)	-150151 (51)	Run 6.4	7000ft	210 deg
150923 (52)	-152929 (56)	Profile P5	FL150->50ft	070 deg
152929 (56)	-160539 (57)	Profile P6	50ft->FL270	080 deg
164938		Land at LYNEHAM		

AsXX EGRR

07 APR 00 Z

METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 75

Standard Parallel Projection, Standard Parallel 20°N, Original scale 1:20m

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

Fs XX EGRR

08 APR 00Z

T+24

Projection: Standard Parallel 40°N, Original scale 1:200,000

7 APR '94 7:46 FROM MET. RESEARCH FLIGHT TO MPF-BOSCOM PAGE 002

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SC
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INT

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: VACC Date: 7/4/94
Flight No: A320 Page 1 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
09:36:43 09:52								TAKE OFF Boscomb.	
09:53:19	00	X	9.9	P	275	51.08 -3.37		7/8 sc below 1/8 cu ^{just} above at	
10:06:45	01	P1	50p	R	279	51.09 -4.57		000 sea state 7 4/8 cu above, clear above.	
10:11:17	01	P1	5.2	P	275	51.11 -4.96		7/8 cu clear above profile through cloud gap clear air top	
10:15:50	01	P1	9.2	P	272	51.08 -5.40		6/8 cu below clear above - very clean air.	
10:20:11	01	P1	13.7	P	273	51.05 -5.87		4/8 cu below clear above.	
10:25:45	01	P1	19.3	P	273	51.03 -6.46		3/8 cu below just passed through thin brown layer horizo	
10:26:26	02	P1	200	P	280	51.0 ..		end of profile.	
10:33:26	02	X	200	F	286	50.99 -7.30		1/8 cu below in streets haze layer just below ws.	
10:51:35	02	X	200	F	287	50.99 -9.18		3/8 cu below thick haze layer just below mixing diagram and elevated PCASP	
								clear above.	
10:57:20	02	X	200	F	287	51.01 -9.51		3/8 sc below the haze layer is still there, but less pronounced. Clear above.	

10:40 to 5:00
11:35

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Lange

Project: VACC Date: 7/4/94
 Flight No: A320 Page 2 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:16:58	02	X	200	F	278	51.04	-11.91	1/8 cu 2/8 sc below.	
11:26:04	02	X	200	FL	297	51.28	-12.79	3/8 sc below. Some haze clear above.	
11:30:08	02	X	200	FL	297				
11:35?	03	P2	200	FL	243	51.39	-13.59	4/8 sc below. 7/8 large patches Ci on horizon	
11:40:21	03	P2	146	FL	239	51.16	-13.91	7/8 sc below of Ci above.	
11:50:10	04	P2	60	F	242	51.11	-14.53	interrupting profile to to turn back, base sc deck had become broken.	
11:51:35	05	P2	460	F	048	51.05	-17.49	7/8 sc below, 4/8 ci above. 5400 cloud tops	
11:53:23								cloud top entry.	
11:55:54								3530 ft. main cloud base	
12:01:51	06	P2	400	R	150	50.82	-13.62	3/8 cu above.	
12:02:57	07	P2	50	R				end of profile	
12:04:02	07	R81	100	R	132	50.73	-13.45	1/8 cu above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kouze

Project: NAEE Date: 7/4/74
 Flight No: A320 Page 3 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:06:03		K81.1	100	R		50.65	-13.33		
12:08:36		K81.2	100	R		50.64	-13.32		
								Loiter while repairs made to ASAS-PX.	
12:38:00		R2.1	100	R		50.94	-13.97	6/8 Sc above.	
12:43:04		R2.1	100	R		50.67	-13.51	7/8 Sc above.	
12:49:15		R2.2	100	R		50.72	-13.48	4/8 around us clear overhead.	
12:50:16		R2.2	100	R	320	50.85	-13.11	3/8 w. above.	
12:52:42		R2.3	100	R	207	50.72	-13.19	6/8 w/sc above. very few white caps on surface.	
12:57:42		R2.3	100	R	207	50.58	-13.28	4/8 w/sc & wave, more white caps and wind streaks on surface.	
12:59:53		R2.4	100	R	255	50.56	-13.27	4/8 w/sc above	
13:04:53		R2.4	100	R	58	50.74	-12.95	4/8 Sc above hazy.	
13:08:21		R3.1	1000	P	215	50.70	-12.98	7/8 Sc ahead	

4
 1000
 2000
 3000
 4000

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Lange

Project: VACC Date: 7/4/94
 Flight No: A320 Page 4 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:15:32	21	R3.1	1000	P	-	50.42	-13.11	Hazy - 4/8 cu with a above.	
13:15:42	22	R3.2	1000	P		50.48	-13.18	Hazy 6/8 sc.	
13:20:44	23	R3.2	1000	P	15	50.70	-12.94	Hazy 5/8 sc above. clear above that through the cloud.	
13:22:26	24	R3.3	1000	P	221	50.69	-13.13	7/8 sc above.	
13:27:26	24	R3.3e	1000	P	167	50.41	-13.10	7/8 sc above.	
13:28:51	25	R3.4	1000	P	45	50.45	-13.01	6/8 sc above.	
13:35:51	26	R3.4e	1000						
13:37:21	27	R3.3	1000	P	27	50.44	-12.72	3/8 sc above. base 3500	4000 6500
13:44:33	30	R4.1	2000	P	60	50.40	-12.95	.	
13:49:54	31	R4.1e	2000	P	357	50.57	-12.61	7/8 sc above. hazy below cloud.	
13:51:48	32	R4.2	2000	P	224	50.53	-12.67	7/8 sc	
13:56:48	33	R4.2	2000	P	310	50.28	-12.41	6/8 sc	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: VACC Date: 7/4/94

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kenye

Flight No: A320 Page 5 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:58:25		R4.3	2000	P		50.31	-12.70		
14:05:25		R4.3 ₂	2000	P		50.49	-12.52	6/8 Sc above.	
14:05:32		R4.4	2000	P	200	50.48	-12.58	7/8 Sc above.	
14:10:42		R4.4 ₂	2000	P		50.17	-12.61	6/8 Sc. Contrails visible through gaps.	
14:12:13		R5.1	4000	P	30	50.21	-12.66	In cloud.	
14:22:36		R5.1 ₂	4000	P	23	50.63	-12.14		
14:25:26		P4.1	7000	P	210	50.55	-12.07	8/8 Sc/cu below, 1/8 ci above.	
14:30:11		P4.2	2800	P	210	50.29	-12.24	7/8 Sc above.	3300 bar (2800)
14:35:28		P4.2	7000	P	210	50.04	-12.40	6/8 Sc below thinner at this end than other. tops 5.5 general contrails over 6K.	
14:37:36		R6.1	7000	P	38	50.11	-12.38	5/8 Sc 1/8 ci above.	
14:42:30	45	R6.1 ₂	7000	P	4			7/8 Sc. below	
14:44:08	46	6.2	7000	P	200	50.25	-12.12	7/8 Sc. below	

14:22:36
14:25:26
14:30:11
14:35:28
14:37:36
14:42:30
14:44:08

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AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kuyk-

Project: VACC

Date: 7/4/94

Flight No: A320

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:49:07	47	R6.2	7000	P	213	49.96 -12.20	6/8 Sc below large wholes Ci above with wave structure.		
14:50:35	48	R6.3	7000	P	29	50.01 -12.21	6/8 Sc		
14:55:36	49	R6.3 _e	7000	P	2	50.23 -11.97	5/8 Sc below 3/8 Ci above waves visible.		
14:56:49		6.4	7000	P	199	50.20 -12.02	.		
15:01:51		R6.4 _e	7000	P	201	49.89 -12.09	4/8 Sc below 1/8 Ci above.		
15:09:23		P5	15000	P	61	50.11 -12.36	2/8 cu in streets below 5/8 Ci above.		
15:15:30	52	P5	8700	P	60	50.23 -11.77	4/8 cu below.		
15:19:16	53	P5	5600	P	58	50.24 -11.41	in cloud P5ASP jump peak near cloud top.		
							5000 into cloud. 3400 cloud base		
15:29:28	56	P5	5000	R	57	50.50 -10.59	6/8 Sc above some brown haze. Ci 8 sea state 5		
15:32:01	57	P6	1800	R	52	50.56 -10.31	in rain under Cu. 3.5 TRUE 36 KTS.		
15:35:29	56	P6	2900	R	63	50.60 -10.09	4/8 Sc thin Sc above thick band of Sc ahead. heavy.		

16:32
16:35

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: VACC Date: 7/4/94
Flight No: A320 Page 7 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
								PCASP peak at about 2000 ft.	
15:44:35	56	P6	8900	FL	65	50.75	-9.27	1/8 cu below in bands below haze band on horizon clear above.	
15:47 ?								Brown layer showed up on PCASP.	
15:51:24	56	P6	15200	FL	61	50.88	-8.61	2/8 sc below the some brown haze clear above.	
15:57:47	56	P6	21300	FL	64	51.01	-7.92	1/8 sc below brown haze layer clear above.	
16:03:28	56	P6	25700	FL	73	51.05	-7.20	2/8 sc below.	
16:05:39	57	P6	270	FL	77	51.05	-6.80		
16:12:03	57	PX	270	FL	73	51.04	-5.99	2/8 sc below with some cu bubbling up.	
								END OF SCIENCE.	

16:28

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Offset = +3

Flight No. A320

Date: 07/06/94

Operator: Helmut

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SET.	CONC/CC	MAX SET.	R eff	CONCA	MAX SET.	CONCP	MAX SET.	
0900										Pre-flight - PCASP cal V = 8.2 (ish)
0950	19	0.25	0.01	0	0	17				
0955	158	0.35	0.01	0	0	10				
1005	167	1.2	0.3	9.5	4.5	-				Start PI 50' T
10.06.46	150	2.2	0.5			0				Start PI 50' T
10.07	150	1.5	0.5			2.0				1000'
10.09	125	2.2	0.07			0				5000'
10.11	80	1.3	-			-				5000'
10.13	25	0.7	-			-				7000'
10.15	15	0.4	-			-				7000'
10.17	50	0.5	-			-				FL 11000' - peak in PCASP @ 1011 125/CC
10.19	70	0.5	-			-				FL 130'
10.21	80	2.2	-			-				FL 150'
10.23	50	0.4	-			-				FL 170'
10.25	200	1.2	-			-				FL 190' - PCASP peak 10.26 - compared to (same peak?)
10.26.26	50	0.4	-			-				FL 200' end PI
10.33	30	0.5	-			-				PCASP steady, no wet 4 min
10.37	30	0.4	-			-				PCASP " " end 4 min
10.39	20	0.6	-			-				"step up" at 20.39
10.43	70	0.4	-			-				slightly increased
10.46	80	0.6	-			-				increased up to 120/CC, now falling again
10.49	200	1.0	-			-				"step up" after (not so steep) steady around 250
10.54	200	0.5	-			-				slight slightly, steady around 200
11.00	20	0.8	-			-				slightly steady
11.02	130	0.8	-			-				dropped suddenly, no visibility 3000' 150'
11.05	110	0.5	-			-				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Offset = +3

Flight No. H320

Date: 07/04/94

Operator: Helen R

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	
1110	100	0.6	-			-				PLAS steady around 100
1127	100	0.4	-			-				" " " "
1129	60	0.5	-			-				PLAS dropped, now steady 2-60 (change to standard)
113462	70	0.6	-			-				FL700 - F50' Start P2. TAS 196
1136	80	0.8	-			-				FL180
1138	100	1.7	-			-				FL160
1140	110	1.7	-			-				FL140
1142	200	0.6	-			-				FL120
11453	75	0.6	-			-				FL110
1146	130	0.6	-			-				FL100
1146	150	0.4	-			-				FL080
114	490	0.5	-			-				FL060
12007	540	0.5	-			-				FL060 intercept P2
12136	600	0.5	-			-				restart P2 TAS 198.
1153	50	0.5	100			200				FL040 into cloud
1155	330	2.5	40			70				leaving cloud FL030
1157	475	2.0	100			150				FL020 into cloud briefly
1159	500	2.2	-			-				FL010 PLAS steady now
120259	475	2.2	-			-				50'
120402	400	2.2	-			-				start R1.1 100'
120603	325		-			-				end R1.1
120836	450	1.3	-			-				start R1.2 100'
1209	800		-			-				strange spike
1210	400	2.2	-			-				steady + 75/cc max
1213	450	2.2	-			-				" " "
1216	430	2.1	-			-				" " "
1230	450	2.2	-			-				problems with VACL - PLAS steady

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* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Offset = 3

Flight No. A320

Date: 07/04/94

Operator: Allen L

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GMT	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SET	CONC/CC	MAX SET	R off	CONCL	MAX SET	CONC/P	MAX SET	
123803	390		-			1000'				start R2.1 100' 2dc spikes - see spray??
1240	350	1.3	-			750'				
1242	380	2.7	-			700				
124306	330		-			-				end R2.1
124516	360	2.7	-			-				start R2.2 100'
1247	350	2.7	-			-				PCASP steady
125016	340	2.2	-			260				end R2.2
125212	360	2.2	-			200				start R2.3 TWS 88
1254	390	2.2	-			130				
1256	350	2.7	-			100				
125749	330	2.2	-			50				end R2.3 100'
125956	330	1.7	-			-				start R2.4
1302	350	2.2	-			-				
130456	380	2.2	-			-				end R2.4 100'
130727	350	2.2	-			5				start R3.1 1000'
1310	350	1.7	-			200				
1312	350	2.2	-			60				PCASP still steady around 350
131322	360	1.0	-			-				end R3.1
131541	311	2.2	-			-				start R3.2 1000' TWS 91
1317	355	2.2	-			-				small spikes in 2dc
1319	360	2.2	-			-				still st
132045	370		-			-				end R3.2
132227	340	2.2	-			-				start R3.3 1000'
1324	320	1.2	-			180				
1326	300	1.0	-			165				PCASP decreased slightly, appears to be less variation
132735	310	2.2	-			170				end R3.3

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Sheet = 3

Flight No. A320

Date: 07/04/94

Operator: Helen L.

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONCL	MAX SIZE	
132851	300	2.2	-			-				start R3.4 (dip in PCASP brill) TAS 91
1336	320	1.7	-			-				
133351	350	1.3	-			-				end R3.4
133610	300					300				start P3 1000' ↑
1335	250		-			-				2000'
1336	270	1.4	-			-				3000'
1337	680		50			373				into cloud 4000' 3500'
133847	250		150			500				end P3 @ 3500' - out of cloud
134435	310		100 100			80				start R4.1 @ 2000'
1346	350		1.0			126				
1348	330		0.7			-				PCASP steady again
134954	350		0.6			-				end R4.1
135149	320		0.8			135				start R4.2 @ 2000' TAS 92 ms ⁻¹
135449	350		1.1			200				end R4.2
135588	290		1.1			330				start R6.3 @ 2000'
140325	400		1.0			250				end R6.3
140532	341		1.4 1.4			240				start R1.6 @ 2000'
1407	280		0.9			204				PCASP is rising slightly but not level
141032	400		0.8			150				end R1.6
141216	300 300		1.1			150				start R5.1 @ 4000' into cloud
1413	275		0.6			-				out of cloud PCASP falling off
1414	250		80			1900				break in cloud initiating the next cycle
1414	270		100			1400				in cloud between ^{clear} patches
1415	300		20			120				- " " " "
1421	430		2			140				- " " " "
142237	311		100			1300				end R5.1 in cloud

* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Alt = 3

Flight No. A320

Date: 07/04/94

Operator: Helen R

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GMT	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/1	MAX SIZE	
142523	190		-			-				Start P.4.1 ↓
1426	400		-			-				PLASP steadily increasing & levels off
1428	350		-			-				steady about 350
143011	300		1.2			200				end P.4.1 ↓ @ 2800' / Start P.4.2T
1431	1000		150			600				through cloud.
1433	850		200			1600				in knots cloud
1434	250		-			-				end act cloud
1435	160		-			-				end P.4.2 @ 7000'
143733	100		-			-				start R6.1 @ 7000' TRAS 100 ms ⁻¹
1440	150		-			-				PLASP steady up to now, starting to increase slightly
1441	180		-			-				
144236	180		-			-				end R6.1
144408	150		-			-				start R6.2 @ 7000'
1447	110		-			190				spikes on Edc
144909	100		-			-				end R6.2
145035	120		-			-				start R6.3 @ 7000'
1453	300		-			-				spike on PLASP
1454	600		-			-				double spike on PLASP
145536	120		-			-				end R6.3
145649	130		-			-				start R6.4 @ 7000'
1458	120		-			1000				spikes on Edc to approx 1000
1501	100		-			2000				" " "
150151	110		-			-				end R6.4
150923	100		-			-				start P5 15000' ↓
1510	180		-			-				14000
1511	160		-			-				13000
1512	90		-			-				12000

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. *A320*

Date: *09/04/96*

Operator: *Helen*

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONCL	MAX SIZE	
1513	70		-			-				11,200'
1514	40									10,000'
1515	40									9,000'
1516	120									8,000'
1517	200									7,000' top edge spikes in 1000'
1518	500		50			2000				6,000' through cloud spikes
1520	400		50			800				5,000' large cloud "
1522	380		20			1100				4,000'
1524	400		1			700				3,000'
1525	390		1			600				2,000'
1527	330		-			3000				1,000'
152929	300		-			4000				9000 end PS 50' start PL ^T
1532	200		-			1200				1,000'
1533	1000		100			3000				spikes on PLFSP - rain drops on edge
1535	150		-			2000				
1537	80		-			2000				spikes on edge PLFSP steadily falling
1539	60		-			300				" " " "
1541	25		-			-				
1543	80		-			70				increasing PLFSP quite rapid
1544	300		-			-				
1544	500		-			-				big ^{double} spike, falling again (large layer)
1547	130		-			-				
1549	90		-			-				
1551	160		-			-				
1554	25		-			-				
1558	100		-			-				
1605.35	30		-			-				end PL ^T PL

* DRS TIME

Run P6 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

Run P1 10:06:46–10:26:26 GMT

Run P2 11:34:42–11:50:02 GMT

Run R2.1 12:38:03–12:43:04 GMT

Run R2.2 12:45:16–12:50:16 GMT

Run R2.3 12:52:54-12:57:42 GMT

Run R2.4 12:59:54-13:04:54 GMT

Run R3.1 13:08:22-13:13:22 GMT

Run R3.2 13:15:41-13:20:45 GMT

Run R4.1 13:44:35–13:49:54 GMT

Run R4.2 13:51:49–13:56:49 GMT

Run R4.3 13:58:25–14:03:25 GMT

Run R4.4 14:05:32–14:10:32 GMT

Run R6.2 14:44:08–14:49:09 GMT

Run R6.3 14:50:35–14:55:36 GMT

Run R6.4 14:56:49–15:01:51 GMT

Run P5 15:09:23–15:29:29 GMT

Run P6 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

Parameter no. 572

Parameter no. 901

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

Parameter no. 905

1 second averages

Parameter no. 919

Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG⁻¹)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM⁻³)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M⁻³)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905

1 second averages

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-12:02:57 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R2

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1612
Mean 50.7480
Standard dev 9.023640e-02
Max value 50.9577
Min value 50.5823

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1612
Mean -13.2822
Standard dev 0.153647
Max value -12.9170
Min value -13.5553

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1612
Mean -35.7379
Standard dev 22.1506
Max value 37.7031
Min value -53.6650

12:38:03 12:44:45 12:51:28 12:58:11 13:04:54
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1612
Mean 40.3758
Standard dev 21.7522
Max value 111.759
Min value 21.7177

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1612
Mean 1017.55
Standard dev 2.66471
Max value 1019.71
Min value 1008.73

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 1612
Mean 1012.43
Standard dev 2.71071
Max value 1015.73
Min value 1001.59

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R2

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1612
Mean 281.223
Standard dev 0.288456
Max value 281.664
Min value 280.436

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1612
Mean 273.879
Standard dev 0.953598
Max value 276.945
Min value 271.210

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1612
Mean 1.409458e-02
Standard dev 1.112088e-02
Max value 6.053805e-02
Min value -4.508996e-02

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R2

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1612
Mean 4.01013
Standard dev 0.312794
Max value 5.02098
Min value 3.35329

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1612
Mean 0.714583
Standard dev 0.166543
Max value 1.19384
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1612
Mean 6.060596e-05
Standard dev 4.400359e-05
Max value 5.563160e-04
Min value 4.773192e-07

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R2

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1612
Mean 2.38340
Standard dev 0.300421
Max value 4.30542
Min value 1.74999

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1612
Mean 360.351
Standard dev 49.0306
Max value 602.702
Min value 204.445

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1612
Mean 14.2624
Standard dev 7.75410
Max value 49.1741
Min value 2.14165

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R2

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1612
Mean 0.142865
Standard dev 1.632253e-02
Max value 0.240181
Min value 0.104905

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R3

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1530
Mean 50.5564
Standard dev 8.357465e-02
Max value 50.7111
Min value 50.4196

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1530
Mean -13.0203
Standard dev 9.829741e-02
Max value -12.7286
Min value -13.1890

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1530
Mean 231.797
Standard dev 10.1610
Max value 274.145
Min value 207.861

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1530
Mean 306.577
Standard dev 10.9834
Max value 352.786
Min value 282.714

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1530
Mean 985.712
Standard dev 1.19301
Max value 988.527
Min value 980.746

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 1530
Mean 980.581
Standard dev 1.25001
Max value 983.903
Min value 974.303

13:08:22 13:14:44 13:21:06 13:27:28 13:33:51
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R3

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1530
Mean 278.710
Standard dev 0.138279
Max value 278.994
Min value 278.279

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1530
Mean 272.831
Standard dev 0.700825
Max value 275.055
Min value 271.114

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1530
Mean 1.554599e-02
Standard dev 1.042867e-02
Max value 7.246081e-02
Min value -2.378277e-02

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R3

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1530
Mean 3.77977
Standard dev 0.278039
Max value 10.4659
Min value 3.24089

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1530
Mean 0.741196
Standard dev 0.190463
Max value 1.28327
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1530
Mean 6.926552e-05
Standard dev 5.469308e-05
Max value 5.993363e-04
Min value 4.721553e-07

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R3

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1530
Mean 2.43126
Standard dev 0.320036
Max value 4.68364
Min value 1.74999

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1530
Mean 333.686
Standard dev 41.0243
Max value 469.502
Min value 131.196

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1530
Mean 14.6826
Standard dev 8.05429
Max value 58.1138
Min value 2.07199

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R3

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1530
Mean 0.146511
Standard dev 1.765701e-02
Max value 0.233069
Min value 0.107368

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1558
Mean 50.4073
Standard dev 9.111836e-02
Max value 50.5694
Min value 50.1970

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1558
Mean -12.6701
Standard dev 0.101641
Max value -12.4939
Min value -12.9496

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1558
Mean 531.955
Standard dev 11.6779
Max value 560.216
Min value 491.723

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R4

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1558
Mean 603.215
Standard dev 11.7550
Max value 629.955
Min value 565.094

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1558
Mean 950.956
Standard dev 1.33310
Max value 955.555
Min value 947.735

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 1558
Mean 945.853
Standard dev 1.43089
Max value 950.557
Min value 942.220

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R4

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1558
Mean 2.43506
Standard dev 0.319029
Max value 6.56258
Min value 1.74999

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1558
Mean 329.878
Standard dev 35.9364
Max value 482.761
Min value 211.516

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1558
Mean 17.9049
Standard dev 9.21713
Max value 65.1663
Min value 2.35375

13:44:35 13:51:04 13:57:33 14:04:02 14:10:32

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1558
Mean 3.84523
Standard dev 0.194765
Max value 4.42596
Min value 3.25444

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1558
Mean 0.955663
Standard dev 0.238045
Max value 1.78847
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1558
Mean 9.191619e-05
Standard dev 6.865635e-05
Max value 8.376115e-04
Min value 4.670553e-07

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R4

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1558
Mean 275.952
Standard dev 0.119171
Max value 276.391
Min value 275.627

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1558
Mean 272.567
Standard dev 0.631660
Max value 274.318
Min value 270.665

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1558
Mean 1.271155e-02
Standard dev 8.613981e-03
Max value 4.323328e-02
Min value -3.677724e-02

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R4

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1558
Mean 0.155125
Standard dev 1.909268e-02
Max value 0.231239
Min value 0.110564

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94
Run no. R5.1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 624
Mean 3.34506
Standard dev 0.339879
Max value 4.32327
Min value 2.75345

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 624
Mean 28.9621
Standard dev 49.2022
Max value 175.585
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 624
Mean 1.472185e-02
Standard dev 2.880081e-02
Max value 0.149428
Min value 3.387097e-06

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R5.1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 624
Mean 1189.53
Standard dev 16.9089
Max value 1234.49
Min value 1143.21

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 624
Mean 884.007
Standard dev 1.86054
Max value 888.836
Min value 878.995

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 624
Mean 879.153
Standard dev 1.78117
Max value 883.615
Min value 874.269

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R5.1

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 624
Mean 270.825
Standard dev 0.184844
Max value 271.349
Min value 270.200

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 624
Mean 269.899
Standard dev 0.969922
Max value 272.524
Min value 267.803

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 624
Mean 7.049181e-02
Standard dev 8.923142e-02
Max value 0.433940
Min value -2.233509e-03

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R5.1

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 624
Mean 3.14124
Standard dev 1.06771
Max value 5.83811
Min value 1.81779

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 624
Mean 390.920
Standard dev 175.059
Max value 2241.09
Min value 185.440

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 624
Mean 196.596
Standard dev 387.313
Max value 2437.02
Min value 1.86312

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R5.1

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 624
Mean 0.239787
Standard dev 0.161484
Max value 0.676435
Min value 0.105150

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

5.113 x 10⁴ 5.129 x 10⁴ 5.145 x 10⁴ 5.160 x 10⁴ 5.176 x 10⁴
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R6

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1459
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1459
Mean 790.023
Standard dev 0.992481
Max value 793.562
Min value 787.688

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 1459
Mean 785.313
Standard dev 1.05317
Max value 789.143
Min value 783.081

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R6

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1459
Mean 1.38040
Standard dev 5.237700e-02
Max value 1.47456
Min value 1.18680

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1459
Mean 1.667202e-02
Standard dev 1.029870e-02
Max value 7.649907e-02
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1459
Mean 8.462779e-07
Standard dev 1.220325e-06
Max value 9.443487e-06
Min value 4.250854e-07

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R6

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1459
Mean 1.86351
Standard dev 0.408375
Max value 4.74993
Min value 1.74999

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1459
Mean 142.577
Standard dev 40.9693
Max value 570.894
Min value 71.0508

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1459
Mean 1.21380
Standard dev 1.69770
Max value 14.4399
Min value 0.262664

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R6

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1459
Mean 0.102147
Standard dev 1.189336e-02
Max value 0.179749
Min value 8.168399e-02

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R6

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1459
Mean 268.650
Standard dev 0.388177
Max value 269.416
Min value 267.412

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1459
Mean 258.871
Standard dev 0.480095
Max value 259.891
Min value 257.448

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1459
Mean 5.335766e-02
Standard dev 6.737895e-03
Max value 7.638144e-02
Min value 2.994585e-02

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94

Run no. R6

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1459
Mean 50.1277
Standard dev 9.829915e-02
Max value 50.3080
Min value 49.9158

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1459
Mean -12.1283
Standard dev 9.718608e-02
Max value -11.9569
Min value -12.4010

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1459
Mean 2050.04
Standard dev 10.1032
Max value 2073.83
Min value 2014.07

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

51.007 51.053 51.100
CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

-6.56 -5.51 -4.45
CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

0 1750 3500
PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

Parameter no. 575

Parameter no. 576

Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

1 second averages

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

Parameter no. 905

Parameter no. 919

Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

Parameter no. 575

Parameter no. 576

Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
Parameter no. 575

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
Parameter no. 576

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)
Parameter no. 579

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 525

DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 529

J/W LWC (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 535

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

50.32 50.45 50.58
CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

-12.25 -12.15 -12.06
CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

0 1750 3500
PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
Parameter no. 575

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
Parameter no. 576

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)
Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905

1 second averages

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575

1 second averages

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)
Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages
Parameter no. 923

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

50.07 50.29 50.52
CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

-12.5 -11.5 -10.5
CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

0 1750 3500
PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
Parameter no. 575

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
Parameter no. 576

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)
Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 525

DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 529

J/W LWC (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 535

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)
Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)
Parameter no. 905

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
Parameter no. 919

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)
Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

Parameter no. 575

Parameter no. 576

Parameter no. 579

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525

1 second averages

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923

1 second averages

JW

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:06:46-10:26:26 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:34:42-11:50:02 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.1

Times 13:34:19-13:38:47 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P3.2

Times 13:38:47-13:42:36 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.1

Times 14:25:23-14:30:11 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P4.2

Times 14:30:11-14:35:24 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P5

Times 15:09:23-15:29:29 GMT

1 second averages

A320 07-APR-94 Profile P6

Times 15:29:29-16:05:39 GMT

1 second averages